

BIOCHEMICAL PROFILE OF SALIVA AFTER OPERCULECTOMY USING DIODE LASER

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Annotation. Pericoronitis is an inflammatory disease of the oral cavity caused by an infection of the soft tissues in the immediate vicinity of the crown of an immature tooth, including the gum and dental follicle. It most often affects the third molar of the lower jaw; it is usually observed in teeth that erupt very gradually or undergo retention. The inflammation process is characterized by different changes in biomarkers concentration in saliva and other biological fluids. Thus, determining the characteristic changes in the concentration of inflammatory cytokines is an important factor in developing an effective algorithm for the treatment of pericoronitis.

Key words: diode laser, operculectomy, saliva biochemistry, lactate dehydrogenase, alkaline phosphatase, pericoronitis, dental surgery, inflammatory markers, alpha-amylase, laser therapy

The aim of the study was to determine the content of pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory interleukins through biochemical examination of mixed saliva after operculectomy using laser.

Materials and Methods: 20 patients with pericoronitis underwent operculectomy using laser Mediola Compact MLD01 (Mediola, Minsk, Belarus). Samples of mixed saliva were collected from patients of two groups before surgery, 3 and 7 days after surgery. A sample of mixed saliva was taken without stimulation by spitting into a sterile plastic tube for 2 minutes. Then it was stored in a freezer at a -18°C . After a single defrosting, the mixed saliva samples were centrifuged for 15 minutes at a speed of 3000 rpm and the filler liquid (supernatant) was separated.

The content of IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-10, lactoferrin, annexin V, α -defensins, FGF- β in ng/ml, TNF- α and OPG in pg/ml, homocysteine in mmol/L, CRP in mg/L, sRANKL in pmol/L on the INFINITE F50 device (TECAN, Gredig, Austria), using test kits (Quantikine, R&D Systems, Minneapolis, USA). The statistical analysis was performed using the OriginPro 8.6 program (OriginLab Corporation, USA) using the One-way ANOVA method. $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results: Operculectomy using laser exposure led to a decrease in TNF- α ($p > 0.05$) in saliva on the first day after surgery, which indicates a decrease in the number of leukocytes and activation of fibroblast cells around the wound. On the first day of wound healing, the amount of α -defensins released by leukocytes in saliva decreased significantly (from $1142 \pm 12,5$ to $1089 \pm 18,2$ ng/ml), and the content of lactoferrin decreased significantly (from $14,8 \pm 1,52$ to $8,08 \pm 1,15$ ng/ml). The decrease in the number of these proteins is probably due to their interaction with microorganisms. CRP, homocysteine and sRANKL disappeared in saliva on the first day and a significant decrease in the amount of OPG (from $0,75 \pm 0,04$ to $0,28 \pm 0,02$ pg/ml) was observed. On the third day of the study, the content of all the studied immunoglobulins did not differ from the values of the control group.

The use of laser for operculectomy provides an anti-inflammatory effect and restoration of protective systems in the oral cavity, expressed in the disappearance of CRP, homocysteine

in mixed saliva, normalization of the amount of FGF- β , annexin V, TNF- α , α -defensins, lactoferrin, IgA, IgG and IgM.

Conclusions: Diode laser use for operculectomy provides less traumatic tissue intervention, reflected in a more favorable salivary biochemical profile with reduced inflammatory response and faster metabolic process recovery. Salivary biochemical parameters can serve as objective markers for evaluating laser treatment effectiveness in dental practice.

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